

BioGOV

Governing Biomodification in the Life Sciences

**Report from the “Governing
Biomodification” (BioGov) End of
Project workshop
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BioGOV End of Project Meeting: Summary Report

1.0 Executive summary

The aim of the project “Governing biomodification in the life sciences” (‘BioGOV’) was to assess the regulatory framework for three emerging ‘biomodifying’ technologies: gene editing, induced pluripotent stem cells and 3D bioprinting. Each is an emerging technology with significant scientific, economic and medical potential. The project utilised a combination of legal and regulatory analysis, and empirical social science to understand the formal regulatory frameworks and the incentives, concepts and institutional factors shaping the translation of these technologies from laboratory tools into new potential healthcare products and services.

BioGOV was a collaboration between researchers at the Universities of Oxford, Sussex and York and ran from September 2018 to August 2022. The project was funded by the Leverhulme Trust through project grant RPG-2017-330. The BioGOV end of project meeting took place online on 18 July 2022. The aim of the workshop was two-fold: i) to disseminate key findings from the BioGOV project and, ii) to explore new directions for research, especially with regards to the potential for citizen-centric governance of biomodifying technologies.

The structure of this report echoes those core aims. Section 2 presents the background to the BioGOV project (2.1), summarises its core research goals (2.2), methods (2.3) and findings (2.4). Section 3 then reviews the end of project workshop itself, covering the purpose and scope of the meeting, reports the content of the two core presentations on the empirical (3.1) and legal/theoretical (3.2) ramifications of the project and the workshop discussions which followed each presentation. Section 4 concludes this report by summarising the range of directions identified for future research on responsible, and citizen-centred governance of technological innovation.

2.0 Background

2.1 What are ‘biomodifying technologies’?

‘Biomodifying technologies’ is a collective label for the various tools and techniques, developed as a result of research in the life sciences, that enable scientists to modify living biological tissue in novel and increasingly customised ways¹. Established examples of biomodifying technologies now in routine use include cell culture (the capacity to grow living material *in vitro*), recombinant DNA (rDNA), the polymerase chain reaction (PCR), and in vitro fertilisation (IVF). For this project we focus on three contemporary examples of emerging biomodifying technologies that have been identified as having potentially far-reaching and transformative effects²: gene editing, induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC) technology, and 3D bioprinting.

¹ Morrison, M., Mourby, M., Bartlett, A and Bicudo, E. (2019) ‘Biomodifying technologies and experimental space.’ Impact: making connections (Ingenta Connect) vol. 2019, no 1, pages 63-65
<https://www.ingentaconnect.com/content/sil/impact/2019/00002019/00000001/art00021>

² Das R. (2016) Five technologies that will disrupt healthcare by 2020. Forbes Available at <http://www.forbes.com/sites/reenitadas/2016/03/30/top-5-technologies-disrupting-healthcare-by-2020/#5758216f6252>; Hochfield W, Riffell J. and Levinson N. (2016) Four treatments that will transform healthcare in Europe in 2016. *European Pharmaceutical Review* 21 (1):12-14; Inoue H, Nagata N, Kurokawa H. and Yamanaka S. (2014) iPSC cells: a game changer for future medicine. *The EMBO Journal* 33(5): 409-417

Gene-editing tools, of which CRISPR/cas⁹ is currently the most prominent example, contain a programmable ‘targeting’ domain that can be designed by scientists to find and attach itself to a particular sequence of genetic material in a living cell, and an enzyme that can cut out that particular piece of DNA, replace it, or change its content (for example, changing an ‘A’ to a ‘T’ in the genetic code). iPSC are a type of stem cell. ‘iPSC technology’ refers both to the method of producing the cells by chemically ‘reprogramming’ adult somatic cells to an embryo-like, pluripotent state, and to the iPSC cells themselves, which can be directed to become many different types of body cell (lung cell, nerve cell, heart muscle cell et cetera). 3D bioprinting is a manufacturing technique which can be applied to different cell types. It is a form of additive manufacturing, where complex three-dimensional constructs are produced by depositing fine layers of material one on top of the other. Bioprinting adapts this technique by replacing plastic or metal as the material to be 3D printed with gel-like suspensions containing living cells, known as ‘bioinks’. The goal is to “transfer the precision, flexibility, speed and agility offered by 3D printers to clinical applications in order to recreate highly complex and heterogeneous structures”.⁴

All three examples can be considered ‘gateway technologies’: versatile, accessible tools which have broad applications, offer advances over existing practices, and which are typically subject to significant commercial activity. Biomodifying technologies are already deployed in a range of sectors. Gene editing can be used to produce genetically modified plants and animals, as well as implementing ‘gene drive’ mechanisms as a tool to control the populations of undesirable ‘pest’ organisms and invasive species,⁵ while stem cell technology and bioprinting are both implicated in the endeavour to create so-called ‘lab-grown’ or ‘in-vitro’ meats as an alternative to traditional livestock farming.⁶ However, in order facilitate an adequately detailed investigation across all three case-study technologies it was necessary to limit scrutiny to one area of potential application: biomedicine. Another feature that makes biomodifying technologies potentially revolutionary is the way each technology platform interacts with the others; for example gene-edited iPSC lines are already being developed as research tools and 3D printing is being designed to create bio-structures from differentiated iPSC.⁷ Another example would be the use of gene-editing techniques to produce iPSCs.⁸ This represents an example of ‘technological convergence’, a term initially developed to describe the merging of previously separate telephone, broadcast (radio and television), and computer technologies in the internet era.⁹

2.2 Why is socio-legal research on biomodifying technologies important?

Prior instances of the application of biomodifying technologies— from genetic engineering to cloning— have shown that they can be culturally and morally controversial.¹⁰ Moreover, studies of extant cases of technological convergence have highlighted their potential for innovation, growth, investment and knowledge production, but also to be highly disruptive: challenging existing organisational practices, scientific fields, markets, and in particular regulatory frameworks.¹¹ Current regulation of innovative technologies within the health sector involves licensing and ethical oversight at the research level and pre-marketing assessment of new medicines

³ CRISPR stands for ‘Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats’ in reference to the characteristic sequence of the RNA ‘targeting domain’.

⁴ Lafontaine, C et al (2021) Bioprinting as a Sociotechnical Project: Imaginaries, Promises and Futures, *Science as Culture*, 30:4, 556-580, DOI: [10.1080/09505431.2021.1977264](https://doi.org/10.1080/09505431.2021.1977264)

⁵ Martin, P. et al, *Genome editing: the dynamics of continuity, convergence, and change in the engineering of life*, 39 NEW GENET. SOC. 219 (2020).

⁶ Stephens, N. et al, *Bringing cultured meat to market: Technical, socio-political, and regulatory challenges in cellular agriculture*, 78 TRENDS FOOD SCI. TECHNOL. 155.

⁷ Faulkner-Jones A. et al (2016) Bioprinting of human pluripotent stem cells and their directed differentiation into hepatocyte-like cells for the generation of mini-livers in 3D. *Biofabrication* 7

⁸ Khan, I.; Hirata, R. et al. 2010. Engineering of Human Pluripotent Stem Cells by AAV-mediated Gene Targeting. *Molecular Therapy* 18(6): 1192-1199.

⁹ Blackman, C.R. (1998) Convergence between telecommunications and other media: How should regulation adapt? *Telecommunications Policy* 22(3): 163-170

¹⁰ Morrison, M and De Saille S. (2019) CRISPR in context: towards a socially responsible debate on embryo editing. *Palgrave Communications* 5, 110: Doi: [10.1057/s41599-019-0319-5](https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-019-0319-5)

¹¹ Blackman 1998 op cit; Hacklin, F., Marxt, C. and Fahrni F. (2009) Coevolutionary cycles of convergence: An extrapolation from the ICT industry. *Change* 76(6): 723-736

and medical devices at the product development stage. These regulatory approaches are highly procedural; based on standards developed for well-defined products and areas of activity and assume a linear model of innovation.¹² However, this conventional review model, with its emphasis on oversight, is not always fit for purpose for governing rapidly advancing gateway technologies linked to diverse product domains and regulatory regimes, but which often raise similar ethical, legal and social challenges. There were therefore good *a priori* reasons to query the adequacy of existing regulatory / oversight frameworks for biomodifying technologies, and the potential for ‘pinch points’ which we define as:

‘Conflicting, overlapping, incoherent or uncertain regulatory frameworks may lead to ‘pinch points’ where otherwise desirable applications of these new technologies are inhibited as an unintended result of the governance framework.’

In this context it is helpful to note Lyra Bennet Moses argument about the role and purpose of regulatory actors:

[T]he primary issue for regulators is not the need to ‘regulate technology’ but the need to ensure that laws and regulatory regimes are well adapted to the sociotechnical landscape in which they operate, which changes over time. As technological practices shift, new harms, risks, market failures and architectures are brought into actual or potential being.¹³

The appropriate targets of regulation are therefore as likely to be human choices, behaviours, and practices as they are material artefacts and processes. To put it another way, it is not the advent of gene editing, iPSC or bioprinting which might prove disruptive but rather their applications and specifically what each of those technologies, alone and in combination, allow people to do to other entities and objects in the world. Moreover, “technological artefacts do not simply fulfil their function, but also produce all kinds of valuable and harmful side effects beyond the goals for which they have been designed or for which they are used”.¹⁴ Accordingly, in order to understand what, if any, potential regulatory pinch points’ might arise, it is necessary to also understand which clinical applications of each biomodifying technology are being developed, as well as what these innovation trajectories look like and how these are being shaped and experienced by different stakeholders in this domain. Accordingly, the BioGOV project has contributed towards:

- A. Developing an overview of which regulatory approaches and governance frameworks currently apply to the development of biomodifying technologies for clinical use within the UK.
- B. Understanding how current frameworks are shaping the development of clinical applications based on each of the platform biomodifying technologies alone and in combination.
- C. Assessing the potential for novel governance approaches, such as adaptive or experimental governance to address current regulatory bottlenecks (‘pinch points’) and alleviate them to yield greater commercial potential from emerging technologies while also addressing regulatory and public concerns about risk, safety, quality and efficacy.

The final aim, (C), also recognised the need to develop more responsive and adaptive regulatory approaches that are sustainable, have methods of assessing risk and complex legal, ethical and social issues across different contexts, include a wide range of stakeholders, are responsive to change and can facilitate rapid implementation of innovation. In dynamic fields such as the environment, ‘adaptive’ governance is increasingly seen as a way to respond effectively to the uncertainty, safety, social concerns, and risk calculations that often accompany the use of new technologies. It advocates self-organisation and de-centralised decision-making as a model for dealing with unforeseen events, by keeping stakeholders close enough to ensure that decision-makers are well informed about the nature and scope of potential risks and the likely effectiveness of solutions.¹⁵ The flexibility

¹² Falk W. and Heinrichs H. (2013) Sharing economy: A potential new Pathway to Sustainability. GAIA 22(4): 228-231.

¹³ Moses, L. B. “Regulating in the face of sociotechnical change” In The Oxford Handbook of Law, Regulation and Technology (2017), p577.

¹⁴Yeung, K. “Are human biomedical interventions legitimate regulatory policy instruments?” In The Oxford handbook of Law, Regulation and Technology (2017), p832.

¹⁵ O’Doherty KC et al (2011) From consent to institutions: designing adaptive governance for genomic biobanks. Social Science and Medicine 73 (3):367–374; Chaffin BC, et al (2014) A decade of adaptive governance scholarship: synthesis and future directions. Ecology and Society 19(3): 56-69.

of adaptive governance is clearly in keeping with theories of ‘experimentalist governance’¹⁶ and ‘participatory governance’.¹⁷ Experimentalist governance being defined primarily in terms of explicit consultation processes between regulators and regulated stakeholders/sectors, and participatory governance being defined in terms of the structural embedding of democratic engagement especially through deliberative practices and citizen involvement. However, adopting such approaches may also pose new challenges for regulators and the regulated. Since the conceptual foundations of these approaches are still novel, there needs to be careful consideration of how to develop and apply robust principles for successful institutional and ideational implementation in the context of emerging biomodifying technologies, which constituted the third strand of research within this project.

2.3 Overview of the BioGOV project

The BioGOV project ran from September 2018 to August 2022. The project was led by Professor Jane Kaye, and was a collaboration between the Universities of Oxford, Sussex and York. The full project team was as follows:

Professor Jane Kaye Dr Michael Morrison Ms Miranda Mourby Dr Jessica Bell ¹	University of Oxford
Emeritus Professor Alex Faulkner Dr Edison Bicudo ² Dr Phoebe Li	University of Sussex
Professor Andrew Webster	University of York

Table 1.0 members of the BioGOV: Governing biomodification in the life sciences project

¹ Currently at Warwick University ² Currently at UCL

The project worked in collaboration with a separately funded piece of research, the ESRC-supported project ‘Biomodifying technologies and experimental space: organisational and regulatory implications for the translation and valuation of health research’ (grant no ES/P002943/1), which ran from 2017 to 2020.

2.3.1 Empirical data collection

An extensive set of qualitative interviews with a range of actors was conducted. Interviews in the qualitative arm of the BioGOV project were led by Dr Edison Bicudo and were supplemented by interview data from the ESRC Biomodifying technologies project (BioMod), which was produced by Dr Michael Morrison, Dr Andrew Bartlett (University of York), Professor Alex Faulkner, Dr Phoebe Li and Professor Andrew Webster. The number of interviewees of different types is summarised in Table 1.0 below.

Interviewee type	Number of interviews	Project of Origin
Academic or clinical scientists working with gene editing	9	BioMod
Companies involved with gene editing	6	BioMod
Academic or clinical scientists working with iPSC	9	BioMod

¹⁶ Sabel CF. and Zeitlin J. (2008) Learning from difference: the new architecture of experimentalist governance in the EU. *European Law Journal* 14(3): 271-327.

¹⁷ Fischer F. (2012) Participatory governance: from theory to practice. In: Levi-Faur D. (ed.). *The Oxford Handbook of Governance*. Oxford Handbooks Online.

Companies involved with iPSC	7	BioMod
Academic or clinical scientists working with 3D bioprinting	23	BioMod BioGOV
Companies involved with 3D bioprinting	8	BioMod BioGOV
Representatives of UK or EU regulatory bodies	15	BioMod BioGOV
Representatives of patient groups and charities	8	BioGOV
NHS managers and staff	7	BioGOV
Other governance actors including intellectual property experts and representatives of university TTOs	10	BioMod BioGOV
TOTAL	102	

Table 2.0 Number of interviews per category

The majority of interviews were conducted in the UK by members of each project, including but not limited to, the authors. For BioGOV, two additional sets of interviews for the bioprinting case study were conducted in Italy (n=7) and in Brazil (n=6). The additional interviews helped boost the number bioprinting companies in our sample; as the most novel of our case-study technologies, it has the least existing social science and legal literature available to supplement and contextualise our own data. Research ethics approval for the study was obtained from the University of Oxford Central University Research Ethics Committee (CUREC) (CUREC reference number R47474) with additional approval for clinical interviews obtained from the Health Research Authority in the UK (IRAS project ID 274135).

Two additional datasets were produced by EB to supplement the legal and interview data:

- 1) Data pertaining to patent applications filed for the three case study technologies. Using two platforms (Google Patents and The Lens), 9,716 gene editing-related patents, 8,336 iPSC-related patents, and 1,301 bioprinting-related patents were identified. This gave an overview of the global patenting scenario, including the consideration of the main patent applicants/holders, and the main patent jurisdictions.
- 2) An analysis of academic papers related to our three case studies. Using Web of Science and Scopus, 12,546 papers related to gene editing, 9,130 papers related to iPSC's, and 1,567 papers related to bioprinting were identified.

These datasets informed the wider analysis of the wider scientific and commercial landscape in which applications of each case study technology was being developed. Direct analysis of this data is presented in Bicudo et al 2020 and Bicudo et al 2022.

2.3.2 Legal research and analysis

Legal research to compile a 'comprehensive map of laws, regulations and regulatory bodies, professional standards' applicable to research and clinical translation of biomodifying technologies in the UK was conducted by Ms Mourby with support from Dr Bell. The legal and regulatory mapping was conducted in a number of stages. An initial map was circulated in November 2018 and discussed at the first project team meeting. Brexit was identified as a key practical issue for the mapping, as it introduced the prospect of a divergence between the UK and EU in terms of legislation and regulatory strategy.

At the time of writing this report, the longer-term consequences of Brexit on UK regulation of biomodifying technologies remain unclear. At the research stage of their development, the Data Protection & Digital Information Bill 2022-2023 offers long-promised liberalisation of UK data regulation; including a more 'relative' definition of identifiable individuals which supports the use of anonymous data in carefully managed

contexts. This was identified as a key driver of cell donation & cell therapies in Miranda Mourby's paper in *Medical Law Review*¹⁸. At the same time, however, our data indicates that development of biomodifying technologies requires information and materials from across a global supply chain, and as such any deviation at the UK level will not fundamentally alter the more precautionary standard of regulation set by the EU.

Likewise, the full implications of the Medicines & Medical Devices Act 2021 have yet to be seen. Despite the broad power to pass Statutory Instruments amending the UK's legal framework, the main initiatives thus far (e.g., broadening 'hub and spoke' dispensing to pharmacies belonging to different legal entities) do not have any immediate relevance in this project.

Given the scale, fluidity, technical detail and uncertain impact of post-Brexit shifts over the lifetime of the project, the decision was taken in 2018 to continue including European Union legislation within the scope of our legal and regulatory mapping. This had the added benefit of widening interest in our findings beyond a purely national level, as evidenced by our ultimate paper in the *Journal of Law and the Biosciences* (accepted by an editorial team based in the U.S).

In 2019, an internal project report focused on mapping key regulatory actors within the UK and EU governance of biomodifying technologies. A key focal point were the assessment systems established under the EU's Advanced Therapy Medicinal Product ('ATMP') Regulation, and in particular the value of the centralised pooling of rare expertise from across Europe on novel technologies via the Committee on Advanced Therapies ('CAT') of the European Medicines Agency ('EMA'). While the CAT was not necessarily taken as an example of ideal governance—focusing, as it does, primarily on technical evidence of physical safety and efficacy, rather than social or ethical implications of a product—our literature and documentary review nonetheless suggested it was a valuable resource for the EU in its attempts to balance access to treatments with patient safety. The adequacy of UK assessment of ATMP's when operating with a smaller pool of evaluative expertise post-Brexit was flagged as a theoretical risk. The EMA's Adaptive Licensing pilot was a key case-study for our analysis of what we termed 'Adaptive Regulation'.

As summarised in the next section, we ultimately found that limitations in the EU's legislative regime were not necessarily the most significant challenge to the clinical translation of biomodifying technologies. Nonetheless, a number of 'pinch points' where gaps, lack of clarity or excessive complexity in existing regulation might inhibit innovation or direct it along socially undesirable paths were identified during the project.

2.4 Overview of key findings

The most substantive 'pinch points' in the present regulation of biomodifying technologies can be summarised as follows:

1. Some *in vivo* gene editing products may not fall within the definition of a Gene Therapy Medicinal Product (GTMP) under the current ATMP regulations. A GTMP is defined as containing, or consisting of, 'recombinant nucleic acid', but it is far from clear that nucleic acids within the CRISPR gene editing tool will always be produced by genetic recombination, and protein-based gene editing tools such as zinc finger nucleases or TALENS could be out of scope altogether if they do not include any nucleic acid. If therapeutic gene-editing compounds fall outside the definition of a GTMP, they would have to be reviewed outside of the specialised scrutiny of the ATMP regulation. The ATMP procedure is intended to be compulsory for advanced therapy medicinal products in order to 'overcome the scarcity of expertise in the Community, ensure a high level of scientific evaluation of these medicinal products'.¹⁹ The narrow definition of GTMPs currently embodied in the ATMP regulation may therefore not be fit for purpose when it comes to gene editing.²⁰

¹⁸ Mourby, M. (2020) Anonymity in EU Healthcare Law: Not an Alternative to Information Governance, *Medical Law Review*, <https://doi.org/10.1093/medlaw/fwaa010>

¹⁹ Council Regulation (EC) 1394/2007 of 13 November 2007 on advanced therapy medicinal products and amending Directive 2001/83/EC and Regulation (EC) No 726/2004 [2007] OJ L324/121, Recital 9.

²⁰ Mourby, M and Morrison, M. (2020) 'Gene Therapy Regulation: Could In-Body Editing Fall Through the Net?' *European Journal of Human Genetics* 28: 979

2. The complexity and many components involved in bioprinting mean that the production and application of a bioprinted construct could potentially fall under the ATMP regulations (for the cells), the Medical Device Regulation (for the software), the Machinery Directive (for the bioprinter itself), and the Computer Aided Design (CAD) file might also contain sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR if it matches features of the patient's biology and/or anatomy.²¹ This complexity also affects issues of product liability, where there remains a need for clarity about what constitutes 'product' in bioprinting (whether it is the 3D bioprinted material; the bioink, the CAD file etc) and who the producer is (the company that owns the patent for the bioprinting process; the laboratory technician performing 3D bioprinting; the hospital/treatment facility itself). Moreover, bioprinting projects use a mixture of proprietary or open source software, but in both cases the majority of software licences or terms and conditions explicitly disavow clinical use and any liability that might result from use to create a clinical product, leaving academic and SMEs with the liability for errors, bugs or inherent flaws in the software code itself if used to 3D print a cellular construct.²²
3. The very existence of bioprinted organs also raises intellectual property rights questions. Naturally occurring human organs are not eligible for patent protection as they are 'products of nature'. Reviewing existing case law pertinent to bioprinting, Lim and Li (2022) conclude that "3D bioprinted human organs may be excluded [from patent eligibility] if it is a claim for a method of treatment by surgery, diagnosis or therapy in the United Kingdom and New Zealand, where legislation provides for an explicit medical treatment exemption. However, if a method claim is construed under the non-surgical aspect of making and printing of a 3D bioprinted human organ (in contrast with the surgical implantation of a 3D bioprinted organ), it could be patentable and not fall under the medical treatment exclusion". Whether or not a bioprinted organ that was identical to a naturally occurring organ would be patentable will be for the patent office, and potentially the courts to decide in each jurisdiction but there are a number of precedents that would suggest that a product claim or composition of matter claim on the organ itself would not be valid.²³

However, in addition to these regulatory 'pinch points' our analysis also identified a number of other, often broader and less clearly defined challenges posed by the clinical application of biomodifying technologies:

1. The issue of how to regulate (and indeed the very moral permissibility) of heritable or reproductive gene editing. This was not originally a core part of the project but was brought into sharp and inescapable relief by the actions of He Jiankui, at whose clinic the world's first genetically edited babies were born in 2018. A further challenge is the difficulty of securing any meaningful 'societal consensus' on reproductive gene editing, especially at a global level.²⁴
2. Several applications of iPSC, gene editing and bioprinting challenge our understanding and definition of 'foundational' concepts that underpin regulatory frameworks, and also often have a more general societal meaning as well, such as 'natural', 'donor' or 'product'. Societal framings of 'nature', 'products' and 'donors' may be tentative and heterogeneous, and will find expression outside academic, policy or regulatory discourse - for example in popular culture and on social media. Tracing these developments

²¹ Li, P. et al. (2020) 3D bioprinting in a 2D regulatory landscape: gaps, uncertainties, and problems, *Law, Innovation and Technology*, 12:1, 1-29, DOI: 10.1080/17579961.2020.1727054; Bicudo, E., et al (2021). Software, risks, and liabilities: ongoing and emergent issues in 3D bioprinting. *Journal of Risk Research* 24, 1319-1334. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2020.1848904>; Nielsen, et al, (2021) Bespoke regulation for bespoke medicine? A comparative analysis of bioprinting regulation in Europe, the USA and Australia. *Journal of 3D printing in medicine* 5, 155-167. <https://doi.org/10.2217/3dp-2021-0011>

²² Bicudo, E., et al (2020): Software, risks, and liabilities: ongoing and emergent issues in 3D bioprinting, *Journal of Risk Research*, DOI:10.1080/13669877.2020.1848904

²³ Lim, P.H. and Li, P. (2022) "Chapter 4: Patentability of biofabricated human organs: products of nature or products derived from nature revisited" In Hawkins, N. (Ed) *Patenting biotechnical innovation: Eligibility, Ethics and Public Interest*. Edward Elgar; Cheltenham UK; pp69-88.

²⁴ As Ref 9

with sufficient accuracy to provide a reliable barometer for the law is thus a complex proposition and may require new forms of governance.²⁵

3. Mechanisms such as the patent system favour a “‘logic of experimentality’, whereby social and political issues are overshadowed by a market rationale”. As a result, control over the innovation trajectories and accessibility of biomodifying therapies tends to lie with a limited number of powerful well-resourced actors in the private sector and tends to operate through transactions that are neither transparent nor accountable except to shareholders.²⁶

These findings point to a different kind of challenge to the regulatory ‘pinch points’ as defined above. They speak to the limitations of our original focus on pinch points as arising only from overlapping, contradictory or inconsistent *regulation*, and indeed to the limits of regulation itself.

3.0 Future directions and the agenda for the end of project workshop

In the original grant application to the Leverhulme Trust, we stated that a key aim of the project was the identification of ‘pinch points’ between the current governance of these technologies and their successful implementation for patients. In other words, we set out to identify points in the legal landscape where regulatory uncertainty, or excessive regulatory burden, threatened to impede socially or commercially desirable application of biomodifying technologies. Some areas of regulatory incompatibility have been identified, as discussed above.

However, for the most part the ‘pinch points’ we originally set out to identify are not the straightforward regulatory deficiencies we might have imagined. Instead, we have found extensive evidence of Adaptive Regulatory practices which:

- 1) Widen the cast of stakeholders engaged around biomodifying technologies.
- 2) Bring evidential flexibility to the clinical evaluation of biomodifying therapies, which includes the creation of spaces for a dialogue between regulators and developers.
- 3) Promote collaboration and consistency between the regulatory bodies involved in the assessment pathway.

As such, our ‘pinch points’ are more multifaceted than simple flaws in legislation or regulation. The points of awkwardness in the clinical translation of these technologies stem more from international ‘hands’ of the market in shaping, patenting and reimbursing them as medical products. There are also more long-term challenges to social understandings of the basic concepts that underpin legislative and regulatory frameworks—particularly ideas such ‘natural’, ‘medicine’, ‘manipulation’, and ‘manufacturing’—that indicate more complex downstream disconnects between the legislative framing of biomodifying therapies and how patients may experience them. These social and economic challenges may—we suggest—go beyond the limit of what formal regulation can address and suggest a role for (Adaptive) Governance after all. These next steps are the impetus behind the end of project workshop, whose aims were to consider what this role may be, and to help identify and refine directions for further research.

The workshop was organised to draw on the multi-disciplinary expertise of invited attendees to consider the implications of our empirical and theoretical findings for the translation of gene-editing, bioprinting and iPSC. The aim was to go beyond the regulatory ‘pinch points’ which were the focus of the original grant application to the Leverhulme Trust, and to think more broadly about the international socio-economic-technical matrix within which health technology regulation forms only one formative element. The intention was to summarise the project’s conclusions and to identify pending questions that could be explored in future studies. While the factors which influence the clinical implementation of biomodifying technologies are evidently very broad, we

²⁵ Mourby, M et al (2022). Biomodifying the ‘natural’: from adaptive regulation to adaptive societal governance. *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, 1–28
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jlb/ljac018>.

²⁶ Bicudo, E. et al. (2022). Patent power in biomedical innovation: technology governance in biomodifying technologies. *The Journal of World Intellectual Property*, 1–22.

wanted to give specific consideration to the role of citizens within this matrix, and how this could provide a launching point for further work.

The BioGOV end of project meeting took place online on 18 July 2022. Fifteen participants including project members, and invited experts in law, regulation, and health policy. The morning session of the workshop was organised into two presentations; the first from Michael Morrison, drawing on the empirical analysis conducted during the BioGOV project and the second from Miranda Mourby setting out the legal and theoretical rationales for adaptive societal governance. Following each presentation there was a group discussion session where participants could post questions and ideas on a virtual post-it board and then talk through their responses. The content of each presentation and discussion is summarised below. The last, afternoon session of the meeting consisted of a final virtual post-it session and group discussion.

3.1 Empirical Presentations & Discussion

Science and Technology Studies (STS) scholars have long paid attention to what Douglas²⁷ calls the ‘loom’ of science; the social and institutional structures within which scientists must operate. Analysis has often focused on academic scientists, and how structures such as competitive grant funding, university management, career progression structures, journal rankings, as well as more recent policy initiatives to promote open data or translational research, impact scientists’ choices as to which activities are worth pursuing²⁸. These structures are typically durable, permitting them have a sustained effect on behaviour and also to be predicted. They operate by embedding criteria of evaluation in their mechanisms of operation. In other words, they implement and reinforce valuations of what is desirable or worthwhile through the ways they evaluate, reward or devalue different activities. Whether this is the criteria for what makes a paper suitable for publication in a high impact journal, a successful grant application, or a professorship, and so on. These factors do not *determine* human choices, but they strongly influence them. Moreover, they can circumscribe courses of action that fall outside their criteria for desirability by withholding access to resources, legal permissions to undertake certain activities, and so on.

The same approach is equally applicable to commercial innovation as well as academic science. Medical (bio)technology has an abundance of durable infrastructure of evaluation: regulatory agencies for medicinal products, research ethics oversight for human-subject research, the tools and agencies of health technology assessment, the priorities and assessment criteria of venture capital firms and other investors, healthcare markets, patents, and the patent system²⁹. Some of this spectrum of institutions, regulations, and policies forms infrastructure dedicated to the evaluation of technologies, other parts are dedicated to the e/valuation of companies, or of activities such as clinical trials or marketing.

We can theorise the *de facto* governance³⁰ of biomodifying technologies as the cumulative results of actors’ attempts to navigate this complex and fragmented system of evaluations, spread across public and private sectors, using different, and potentially widely divergent criteria for what is worthwhile and how this should be

²⁷ Douglas, H. (2018). From Tapestry to Loom: Broadening the Perspective on Values in Science. *Philosophy, Theory, and Practice in Biology*, 10(20220112). <https://doi.org/10.3998/ptpbio.16039257.0010.008>

²⁸ Fochler, M. (2016). Variants of Epistemic Capitalism: Knowledge Production and the Accumulation of Worth in Commercial Biotechnology and the Academic Life Sciences. *Science Technology and Human Values*, 41(5): 922–948. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243916652224>; Hessels, L. K et al. (2009). In search of relevance: The changing contract between science and society. *Science and Public Policy*, 36(5): 387–401. <https://doi.org/10.3152/030234209X442034> ; Levin, N. and Leonelli, S. (2017). How Does One “Open” Science? Questions of Value in Biological Research. *Science Technology and Human Values*, 42(2), 280–305. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243916672071>

²⁹ Lehoux, P et al (2014). How do business model and health technology design influence each other? Insights from a longitudinal case study of three academic spin-offs. *Research Policy*, 43(6): 1025–1038. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2014.02.001> ;Lehoux, P. et al (2017). Providing value to new health technology: The early contribution of entrepreneurs, investors, and regulatory agencies. *International Journal of Health Policy and Management*, 6(9): 509–518. <https://doi.org/10.15171/ijhpm.2017.11>; Lehoux, P et al (2016). How venture capitalists decide which new medical technologies come to exist. *Science and Public Policy*, 43(3): 375–385. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scv051>

³⁰ Van Lente, H. and Rip, A. (2017) “Reflexive co-evolution and governance patterns” In D.M. Bowman, E. Stokes and A. Rip (Eds) *Embedding new technologies into society: A regulatory, ethical and societal perspective*. Pan Stanford Publishing; Singapore; pp17-34.

measured, weighted and assessed. Therefore, we can position the challenges and emergent issues we identified in BioGOV as misalignments, not only between competing conceptions of ‘value’ in healthcare, but also of dissonant practices and processes of evaluation of different entities (research goals, products, companies, processes, markets etc) in the biomedical innovation space. These groups and institutions will have very different criteria for judging what activities are worth pursuing, hampering the coherence of the overall innovation trajectory.

Finally, when considering how these various discrepancies map onto the concept of citizen-centric governance, it is worth noting that members of the public are involved in some parts of the institutional infrastructure for assessing innovation (particularly within the public sector), but other parts remain opaque and inaccessible to public scrutiny as noted above. This element of incoherence raises the question of whether the public receives the full picture when they are engaged in the governance of biomodifying technologies? Or whether this is an inevitable aspect of any technological innovation, which does not significantly detract from the efficacy of public engagement and involvement by regulatory agencies?

The following questions were posed for discussion:

1. Does the potential exclusion of the public from spaces of value determination (e.g., among funders/investors) undermine the role of citizens in bio-governance?
2. This part of the work is primarily a social science account of ‘what matters;’ to what extent is it compatible with formal definitions of regulation governance and how might that affect its usefulness for regulatory scholars?
3. What regulatory, policy or other measures (e.g., ‘mission orientated innovation’ as proposed by Mariana Mazzucato³¹) might be brought to bear on this innovating environment to overcome ‘pinch points’ that may lead to value for some actors but disbenefits for others?
4. To what extent might it be i) desirable and ii) feasible to extent transparency, accountability and lay involvement in steering the broader trajectories of biomedical innovation?

Much of the discussion focused on the final point 4 on the feasibility and desirability of extending citizen involvement in the governance of innovation. It was recognised that ‘participation’ in governance is distinct from ‘engagement’, and that in effect we are discussing *participation* in the governance of innovation not governance of technology. There is, as discussed in the next section, a potential separation between regulatory issues and societal issues, but the idea of focusing on governance, has potential to extend the scope of oversight beyond traditional regulatory concerns.

Important issues raised included:

- The need for clarity around what role/s it is desirable for citizens to play in governance, and how well (or not) this aligns with the priorities and interests of the public themselves. Given the often highly complicated nature of both technical and policy aspects of innovation, in the face of competing serious issues facing many ordinary people from climate change to the cost of living, there may be a risk of ‘engagement fatigue’, resulting in participation being dominated by those who already have a vested interest in particular outcomes. Equally, it was suggested that participatory approaches also need to manage public expectations around technology, given the hype that often accompanies novel technologies and fields. One option might be to pay people for participation in a fashion similar to participants in health research?
- If a more participatory approach were to be adopted, what processes and mechanisms are available- and cost-effective/sustainable - to actually enable meaningful participation? Any approach needs to recognise that there are multiple ‘publics’ and that to an extent exercises in outreach (whether engagement or participation) construct particular publics through their selection of who is, and is not invited, which voices and issues matter, and how debate is conducted in practice. It was noted that meaningful participation needs to consider different scales from local, national and international, and operate at different states of the innovation process. As with climate change, there is a case for representing the interests of future generations as well as near-term goals.

³¹ Mazzucato, M. (2018) Mission-Oriented Research & Innovation in the European Union. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

- Participation needs to be connected to genuine and meaningful outcomes to be more than merely tokenistic, but for legitimacy it also needs to be inclusive and representative of the diversity of public(s). This requires buy-in from other stakeholders in the innovation process to allow meaningful change. Meaningful impact requires public fora to be allowed to debate and have a say on key drivers of both industry and regulatory action. Questions were raised about how to avoid regulatory ‘capture’ of publics by vested interests (including the state) and as to the details of who should set the questions, terms and scope of discussion as this is not a neutral or self-evident activity. It was also noted that ‘citizen’ may be an overly homogenising term and is not without political connotations (see below). This also requires transparent mechanisms to account for the diversity of values and translate them into a coherent set of recommendations of actions.
- The point was also raised that technological change may itself change the behaviour and attitudes of the public. In the case of human enhancement this might include direct psychological and cognitive modifications as well as the more common shifts in public attitudes that can occur in response to changing conditions.

3.2 Theoretical Presentations & Discussion

The identity and role of the ‘citizen,’ as configured in the context of health technology governance, is a question on which a number of attendees had already published well formulated responses. A ‘bio-citizen’—i.e., an individual with a stake in the future of human biology—could be understood as broadly as anyone with a human genome. However, much of the regulation and decision-making within our focus stems from the European Union, in which the definition and role of European citizenry is a ‘big issue’ in its own right.³² Whether adaptive regulation of medicinal products to include citizens as stakeholders furthers legitimacy,³³ improves regulatory decision-making,³⁴ or takes a flexible evidentiary approach that exceeds the European Medicines Agency’s democratic mandate,³⁵ were open questions.

There are, in essence, two types of issue identified by the theoretical strand of the project, the resolution of which could involve some element of citizen participation:

- 1) Access issues: this boils down to ‘practical’ questions such as:
 - a. In what circumstances should we fund biomodifying technologies as therapies?
 - b. How much evidence do we require of their safety and efficacy?
 - c. How do we balance access and safety in the face of long-term uncertainty as to their impact?
 - d. How does the current reconfiguration of the advanced therapies global market, which shows concentration trends, challenge the promotion of wider access to these therapies?
- 2) Conceptual Issues:
 - a. To what extent do these bio-modifying technologies disrupt our idea of ‘life’, ‘nature’, ‘products’ and what it means to be human?
 - b. What classical concepts (such as democracy and citizenship) and recent concepts (such as biocitizenship and adaptive governance) can help us interpret the social impacts of biomodifying technologies?
 - c. What lines in thought can best help us understand the interface between law, society, and therapy development?

A core conclusion—as refined by the workshop discussions—is that the role of citizens fundamentally differs for these two types of problem. As far as access is concerned, there is a clear role for citizens—and indeed one that could potentially be strengthened in law and the statutes of key institutions such as regulatory agencies, health technology assessment agencies, and patent offices. The latter, however, is a type of problem not

³² Flear, M. (2015) *Governing Public Health* (Hart), 4

³³ Warren-Jones, A. (2017) ‘Health care and health innovation in Europe: regulating for public benefit or for commercial profit?’ 12 *Health Economics, Policy and Law* 403-409

³⁴ Flear, *ibid* note 30

³⁵ Syrett, K. (2020) ‘Regulation, Innovation and Disruption: The European Medicines Agency and Adaptive Licensing of Pharmaceuticals’ 12 *Law, Innovation & Technology* 2

susceptible to final resolution through deliberative exercise. Here, we see an ongoing role for observational social science and reflection from the humanities to complement citizen discourses.

3.2.1 Access Participation

The access vs safety question is not unique to biomodifying therapies. Any solution proposed in this context could therefore have implications for other personalised medicine which cannot be produced in a commercially profitable way, and where citizen involvement may thus compensate for the failures of neoliberalism/free-market forces in healthcare.

It was suggested that a legal right to participate in healthcare decision-making (e.g., priority setting and commissioning) could be part of the solution, although concern was raised at the implications of an individually enforceable right.

There are at least three potential ways in which a right to participation could be framed:

- 1) At an international level, similar to the ‘right to health,’ which seldom translates into a right to any specific outcome (e.g., access to a particular treatment) in a national context. This could provide policy impetus, beyond seeing participatory or collaborative governance as a vague social good but would risk confinement to a primarily symbolic role.
- 2) As a legal obligation on specialist treatment commissioners to include citizen perspectives in their priority-setting, even potentially including some scenarios where the commissioner would be compelled to follow their advice. This might be practicable in countries with nationalised healthcare—indeed NHS England already has some patient representatives in its advisory panel for specialised commissioning.³⁶ It would be less plausibly enforceable in the context of private funders, however.
- 3) As a right—similar to the EU’s ‘citizens’ initiative’—to bring proposals for a specific treatment or pathway to a commissioner’s attention for consideration. This could go beyond exceptional funding requests for individuals and involve patient groups and providers advocating for a specialised treatment to be made routinely available (if very selectively) available at a particular Trust. The greatest risk here is that the commissioner would need to retain the discretion to decline which—as with the EU citizens’ initiative³⁷—could significantly limit its impact in practice.

A legal ‘right’ to participation in bio-governance has some promise but is evidently not without pitfalls. For example, one would need to make sure that patient representation really echoes patients’ needs instead of being somehow diverted by the close collaboration between some patient representation organisations and the industry or by the possible emergence of “professional representatives” whose activities might be captured by other interests. Therefore, this topic requires further research.

3.2.2 Conceptual Participation

Put simply, biomodifying technologies place a new degree of strain on our understanding of naturally occurring ‘life’ as opposed to human-produced ‘products.’ They hold the promise of a more precise and profound degree of biological reformulation than has previously been possible. But they are not unique in their problematisation at a conceptual level, any more than they are in their questions of access. Jasanoff and Hurlbut have argued eloquently for inclusive deliberation around biotechnologies which raise the ‘*central question of how to care for and value human life, individually, societally and in relation to other forms of life on Earth*’³⁸ However, this is echoed in its scope by transformations claimed for other technologies, most notably Artificial Intelligence. Kissinger, Schmidt and Huttenlocher predict that AI will bring about ‘*the alteration of human identity and the human experience of reality*’ requiring societies to ‘*cooperate, not only to understand, but also to adapt.*’³⁹

The case for broad participation in the navigation of these projected shifts is clear, but the form(s) this participation should take is less obvious. No citizen jury will be able to tell us how to care for and value all human life, or how the human experience of reality will alter in the course of the 21st century. Deliberation, as

³⁶ NHS England, ‘Clinical Priorities Advisory Group,’ <https://www.england.nhs.uk/commissioning/cpag/> accessed 5 August 2022

³⁷ Diego González Cadenas, (2020) ‘Facing Democratic Crisis in the EU: the New European Citizens’ Initiative Regulation’ 9 Global Journal of Comparative Law 117-147

³⁸ Jasanoff S. and Hurlbut, J.B. (2018) ‘A Global Observatory for Gene Editing’ 555 Nature 435

³⁹ Kissinger, H et al (2021) *The Age of AI* (John Murray), 4-6

a set of formalised discussions aimed at a question capable of practical resolution, plays a less compelling and plausible role amid this alleged conceptual disturbance.

There is some connection between these wider predicted transformations, and more discrete questions susceptible to deliberation. As pointed out during the workshop, for example, debating biomodification forms a backdrop to the deliberations on climate change (in which context practical solutions *are* necessary) as we determine the extent to which we and/or our global environment should be bio-modified so we can continue to co-exist.

However, the full scale of the social, ethical and humanistic disruption envisaged by a number of authors in response to emerging technologies is profound and widespread and not capable of final resolution within deliberation, or even within a single disciplinary, policy or international discourse. If what it means to be human, alive and part of nature is truly set to be significantly reformulated in the next few decades, this will be reflected in discourses across society, spanning academic reflection, legislative debates and the popular imagination. At present, the most succinct answer we can propose to this conundrum—which exceeds the scope of any one research project—is to reaffirm the value of academic social science and the humanities to observe and highlight these predicted transformations as they play out, and thus play a role in societal coordination to comprehend and adapt to new technologies.

In relation to the political side of biomodifying technologies, there is also much to do in terms of regulations and the oversight of business models. Key technologies (such as the Crispr-Cas9 gene-editing technology) are being rapidly appropriated and protected by a handful of corporations. In this context, there is not much hope that the corporate diversity of some emerging markets (such as bioprinting) will be preserved, which can jeopardise the viability of many middle-sized companies as globalizing trends are reinforced. In this way, policy makers and regulators would benefit from making sure that the development of decisive technologies are not completely closed to public scrutiny and control, as these technologies will be key to tackle global health crises and, possibly, upcoming pandemics.

4.0 Conclusions

In order to frame the conclusions of this report, and the key understandings and guidance for future research gleaned from the end of project workshop, it can first be helpful to recognise a shift in focus from ‘regulation’ (the primary focus of the BioGOV project) to ‘governance’. Definitions of regulation vary, including within regulatory scholarship itself. Under Julia Black’s influential definition, ‘regulation’ can be defined as:

*the sustained and focused attempt to alter the behaviour of others according to defined standards or purposes with the intention of producing a broadly identified outcome or outcomes, which may involve mechanisms of standard-setting, information gathering and behaviour modification.*⁴⁰

Whilst popular, this definition, can potentially encompass a variety of activities that “would not typically be regarded as regulatory either by regulatory governance scholars or in ordinary usage”.⁴¹ Karen Yeung has proposed an alternative definition of ‘regulation’ as “organized attempts to manage risks or behaviour to address a collective problem or concern”.⁴² This aligns more closely with what we see in the regulation of emerging technologies, where regulatory efforts typically focus on the management of risks and uncertainties. In the case of biomodifying technologies there is a considerable amount of ‘inherited regulation’⁴³ which covers collection, storage and research on human tissue, development and pre-market testing of medicinal products, cost-effectiveness of products, post-market surveillance, privacy and data protection, and ethical safeguarding of human subjects in clinical research. This framework – much of which was mapped and assessed as part of the BioGOV project – covers a considerable part of the research and product development pathway, as well as the application and oversight of authorised medicinal products. For the most part it appears to work well for

⁴⁰ Black, J. (2020) *Critical Reflections on Regulation* 27 AUST. J. LEGAL PHILOS. 1.

⁴¹ As ref 13

⁴² Ibid

⁴³ Stokes, E. (2012) Nanotechnology and the Products of Inherited Regulation. *Journal of Law and Society*, 39(1): 93-112.

biomodifying technologies, subject to the limited number of pinch points we identified above. In the UK there is also a considerable degree of adaptive and networked regulation, with different bodies such as the MHRA, HRA, and NICE, sharing information, co-ordinating actions, and reflexively considering the cumulative impact of their regulatory activity.⁴⁴

As is common in biotechnology and life sciences regulation, there is something of a division between formal regulation which focuses on quantifiable, typically physical risks and harms and ‘softer’ ethical oversight which attends to wider societal issues.⁴⁵ For example, members of the public are now involved in some parts of the institutional infrastructure for assessing innovation; the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence has lay members on some of its panels, while bodies such as the Human Tissue Authority or the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency can opt to host period public consultations on specific issues. In a sociotechnical system, particular patterns of interactions become institutionalised to a greater or lesser degree. It is these institutionalised patterns of interaction that Van Lente and Rip characterise as *de facto* governance; “not governance arranged by one or another actor, but governance in and through the pattern”.⁴⁶ One way in which governance mechanisms extend beyond and supplement formal regulation is in these ‘soft’ public and patient involvement and engagement processes. Given this existing institutional framework, potential for greater involvement of citizens in decision-making about access to emerging therapies, through participation in commissioning decisions for example, was considered feasible, though far from straightforward. The challenges, and thus the scope for future research here is primarily about identifying viable, legitimate and sustainable mechanisms and procedures for delivering this type of citizen-centred governance. There may be scope for regulatory experimentation⁴⁷ and also for taking a processual⁴⁸ approach to regulation and governance, which allows feedback loops to modulate and improve practice over time.

From a perspective of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), adequate and careful oversight requires paying attention to *both* direct impacts of innovation (such as access) and wider social aspirations, values and needs over time. In recent decades the latter goal has been addressed by an increase in activities designed to bridge the gap between technology development and society, through engagement with accredited society actors such as NGOs and designated stakeholders, employing deliberative democracy approaches to complement the traditional authority of representative government.⁴⁹ RRI embeds a ‘co-evolutionary’ approaches to technology in which “the development of new technologies is a process in which science, technology and society co-evolve”⁵⁰. Co-evolution entails interdependencies between the social and the technical, and interactions between scientists, technology developers and other social actors. However, the scope and impact of public and patient contributions varies, and deliberative fora seem to lack the adaptive, inter-agency co-ordination that many UK authorities enjoy. As Groves has observed, institutional procedures for anticipating and accounting for the future tend to rely on abstract calculations and as such produce ‘generic’ futures in which individuals are rendered as interchangeable units rather than people or communities with specific, situated affective needs and desires.⁵¹ This creates a gap in governance – beyond what formal regulation can address – as the capacity for debating some of the wider social implications of changes to foundational concepts such as ‘nature’ or ‘donation’ gets squeezed out of official channels (see challenge 2# above). Addressing this challenge is arguably more complex than devising more citizen-centric priority setting in commissioning decisions, as it requires both conceptual

⁴⁴ As Ref 22

⁴⁵ Levidow, L. and Carr, S. How biotechnology regulation sets a risk/ethics boundary. *Agriculture and Human Values* 14, 29–43 (1997). <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1007394812312>; and see also Ref 9.

⁴⁶ Ibid.

⁴⁷ Ranchordas, S. (2021) Experimental law-making in the EU: Regulatory Sandboxes. *EU Law Live* [Weekend Edition, 22 October 2021], University of Groningen Faculty of Law Research Paper No. 12/2021, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3963810> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3963810>

⁴⁸ Concept Note “Processual regulation of health research” Liminal Spaces project. Edinburgh Law School; Edinburgh. Available at: <https://www.law.ed.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2021-03/Processual%20regulation%20concept%20note.pdf>

⁴⁹ As ref 24

⁵⁰ Ref 24 page 18.

⁵¹ Groves, C. (2017) Care and techno-science: Re-embedding the futures of innovation. In D.M. Bowman, E. Stokes and A Rip (Eds) *Embedding new technologies into society: A regulatory, ethical and societal perspective*. Pan Stanford Publishing; Singapore; pp89-114.

clarifications, in terms of both legitimacy and scope, and assessment of appropriate practical mechanisms, and as yet only tentative avenues for specific future research were discussed.

Lastly, other parts of sociotechnical system through which biomodifying technologies are developed and commercialised remain opaque and inaccessible to public scrutiny. For example, most commercialisation of biomodifying technologies is undertaken by small-to medium sized firms (SMEs), albeit the majority of companies on our study were limited to firms with at least one office or facility in the UK, and which are commercialising some aspect of either gene editing, iPSC or bioprinting for an application relevant to human health. Typically, the basis for commercialisation is novel findings or techniques from publicly funded academic research, although small companies are also ‘spun-out’ from existing firms, to develop new products or services which arise from in-house research but diverge from the core business of the original firm. In both cases, intellectual property rights, primarily patents and license agreements, are at the heart of the commodification of knowledge and its transfer from one entity (a university or parent company) to another.⁵² During this phase, firms must secure investment from third parties to survive and grow. For SMEs seeking to commercialise biomodifying technologies, investors are an important external audience who must be engaged and impressed. There are a variety of professional investors including venture capital companies which strategically invest capital pooled from multiple sources, ‘angel’ investors who are often high-net worth individuals investing their own money, hedge funds, investment banks, private equity firms, large incumbent firms such as pharmaceutical companies, and ‘business incubators’ which may be funded through governments or universities. One thing all these entities have in common is that they are looking to secure a profitable return on their investment. Investors typically invest in return for equity – that is for a share of the company’s net worth at whatever point they sell their stake. Venture Capital investors also usually take a seat on the board of companies they invest in and actively intervene in decisions such as appointment of other senior executives or the company’s approach to market. Investors thus not only provide financial support, but they also actively transform the value proposition of technologies being developed by the firms they choose to support: “from an investment standpoint, the technology a venture is developing has no intrinsic value: it is neither good nor bad. The issue is whether it can “find its purchaser” and sell”.⁵³ Thus, for investors – who are also viewing investments choices as part of the portfolio – market value is more significant than clinical or societal value of a technology.

Financial decisions about which firms to invest in, or how to orientate a firm’s R&D towards the market are typically considered matters of ‘private governance’, outside the scope of regulation *per se*. This problem has been recognised in relation to other novel technologies. For example, in relation to AI development, Mittelstadt has noted the discrepancy between oversight of medicine and healthcare (including research) and private sector actors:

Equivalent fiduciary relationships and complementary governance mechanisms do not exist for private sector AI developers. AI developers do not commit to public service, which in other professions requires practitioners to uphold public interests in the face of competing business or managerial interest [...] Companies and their employees have principal fiduciary duties towards their shareholders. Public interests are not granted primacy over commercial interests.⁵⁴

Governance thus encompasses a mixture of public and private, regulatory and non-regulatory activities, and intended and unexpected consequences. However, this does not *a priori* mean that they do not, or should not raise concerns about transparency, democratic accountability and the public good. If we consider Yeung’s definition of regulation, might we not consider that access to medicines, and the very nature of those medicines, is itself a collective problem with attendant risks that could warrant the extension of democratic accountability and a legitimate public interest even into the self-interested activities of private sector actors? Similarly, theories of participatory, and to an extent adaptive, governance approaches extend the normative claim that public and citizen involvement in technology and innovation *is* warranted and legitimate. A third, and also difficult avenue

⁵² Parthasarathy, S. (2017). Patent politics: life forms, markets, and the public interest in the United States and Europe. University of Chicago Press; Hilgartner, S. (2009). Intellectual Property and the Politics of Emerging Technology: Inventors, Citizens, and Powers to Shape the Future. *Chicago-Kent Law Review*, 84(1), 197–226; and see Ref 23

⁵³ Lehoux, P., et al. (2017) Providing Value to New Health Technology: The Early Contribution of Entrepreneurs, Investors, and Regulatory Agencies. *International Journal of Health Policy Management*, 6(x), 1–10; doi 0.15171/ijhpm.2017.11

⁵⁴ Mittelstadt, B. (2019) Principles alone cannot guarantee ethical AI. *Nat Mach Intell* 1: 501–507 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0114-4>

for further research is to explore whether, and if so how, private sector biomedical innovation might be made more accountable to the public interest, especially by non-market mechanisms. This could build on existing suggestions in this direction⁵⁵, but also does not need to be constrained by them.

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⁵⁵ Mazzucato (as Ref 29); Geiger, S. (Ed) (2021) Healthcare activism: markets, morals and the public good. Oxford University Press; Oxford.

Appendix A: List of all BioGOV outputs to date

Journal articles

Bicudo, E. (forthcoming). Cognitive foundations of society: advanced therapies and the concept of schema. *Applied Linguistics*.

Asquer A and Morrison M (2022) Editorial: Regulation and governance of gene editing technologies (CRISPR, etc.). *Front. Polit. Sci.* 4:1027410. doi: 10.3389/fpos.2022.1027410

Bicudo, E. and Brass, I. (2022) Institutional and infrastructure challenges for hospitals producing advanced therapies in the UK: the concept of 'point-of-care manufacturing readiness' *Regenerative Medicine* 17(10) <https://doi.org/10.2217/rme-2022-0064>

Bicudo, E., Brass, I. and Carmichael, P. (2022) Point-of-care manufacture of advanced therapies: readiness measures for hospitals, companies, and regulatory agencies. *Future Targeted Healthcare Manufacturing Hub*, UCL. Available from: https://www.ucl.ac.uk/steapp/sites/steapp/files/point-of-care_manufacture_of_advanced_therapies_fthm_policy_brief_jul_2022.pdf

Bicudo, E., Morrison, M., Li, P., Faulkner, A., Webster, A., Mourby, M., and Kaye, J. (2022) patent power in biomedical innovation: technology governance in biomodifying technologies. *Journal of World Intellectual Property* 25(2); 473-494.

Morrison, M. and Bartlett, A. (2022) "Making translational value: Identifying 'good targets' for clinical research on gene editing and induced pluripotent stem cell technologies". *Social Science and Medicine Qualitative Research in Healthcare* 2 (December): <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmqr.2022.100131>

Mourby, M., Bell, J., Morrison, M., Faulkner, A., Li, P., Bicudo, E., Webster, A., and Kaye, J. (2022) "Biomodifying the 'natural': from Adaptive Regulation to Adaptive Societal Governance" *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, Vol 9, Issue 1, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jlb/lisac018>

Bicudo E, Faulkner A, Li P. (2021) Digital readiness in 3D bioprinting: software, governance and hospitals' proto-clinical interfaces. *Regenerative Medicine* 16(3): 237-252

Bicudo E, Faulkner, A, Li, P. (2021) Sociotechnical alignment in biomedicine: the 3D bioprinting market beyond technology convergence, *Technology in Society* 66: 1-12

Mahalatchimy, A., Lau, P.L., Li, P. and Flear, M. (2021) Framing and legitimating EU legal regulation of human gene-editing technologies: key facets and functions of an imaginary, *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, Volume 8, Issue 2, July-December 2021, Isaa080, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jlb/lisaa080>

McKeown, A., Mourby, M., Harrison, P. and Harrison, S. (2021) 'Ethical Issues in Consent for the Reuse of Data in Health Data Platforms'. *Science and Engineering Ethics* 27, (9) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-021-00282-0>

Stephens, N., Hogle, L., Morrison, M. and Martin, P. (2021) Spatiotemporal readiness is key to preparing regenerative medicine for the clinic. *Regenerative Medicine* 16(3): 229-235 <https://doi.org/10.2217/rme-2020-0164>

Takashima, K., Morrison, M. and Minari J. (2021). Reflection on the enactment and impact of safety laws for regenerative medicine in Japan. *Stem Cell Reports*, 16(6); 1425-1434.

Umemura, M and Morrison, M. (2021) Comparative lessons in regenerative medicine readiness: learning from the UK and Japanese experience. *Regenerative Medicine* 16(3): 269-282 [0.2217/rme-2020-0136](https://doi.org/10.2217/rme-2020-0136)

Webster, A. and Terzic, A. (2021) Regenerative readiness: innovation meets sociology. *Regenerative Medicine* 16(3): 189–195.

Bicudo, E., Faulkner, A. & Li, P. (2020): Software, risks, and liabilities: ongoing and emergent issues in 3D bioprinting, *Journal of Risk Research*, DOI:10.1080/13669877.2020.1848904

Bicudo, E.; Faulkner, A. and Li, P. (2020) Patents and the experimental space: social, legal and geographical dimensions of 3D bioprinting. *International Review of Law, Computers & Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600869.2020.1785066>

Li, P., Faulkner, A. and Medcalf, N. (2020) 3D bioprinting in a 2D regulatory landscape: gaps, uncertainties, and problems. *Law, Innovation and Technology*, 12:1, 1-29, DOI: 10.1080/17579961.2020.1727054

Morrison, M., Mourby, M., Gowans, H., Coy, S. and Kaye, J. (2020) Governance of research consortia: challenges of implementing Responsible Research and Innovation within Europe. *Life Sciences Society & Policy* 16:13 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40504-020-00109-z>

Mourby, M. and Morrison, M. (2020) Gene therapy regulation: could in-body editing fall through the net? *European Journal of Human Genetics* 28, 979–981. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41431-020-0607-y>

Mourby, M. (2020) Anonymity in EU Healthcare Law: Not an Alternative to Information Governance, *Medical Law Review*, <https://doi.org/10.1093/medlaw/fwaa010>

Book chapters

Lim, P.H and Li, P. (2022) “Chapter 4: Patentability of biofabricated human organs: products of nature or products derived from nature revisited”. In N. Hawkins (Ed) *Patenting Biomedical Innovation: Eligibility, Ethics and Public Interest*. Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd; Cheltenham; pp69-88

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Morrison, M. and Bicudo, E. (2022) Infrastructures of valuation: the social shaping of innovation trajectories in tissue-based industries. European Association for the Study of Science and Technology (EASST) conference, Madrid, Spain, 6-9 July 2022.

Li, P. (2021) ‘Biofabrication governance’, Re-imagining the futures of 3D printing in society Symposium 23-24 March, Virtual Event, Karlsruher Institut für Technologie, Universität Heridelberg, March 2021

Morrison, M. (2021) “Artificial life: the social relations of biotechnology”. Masaryk University, Department of Sociology, Brno (virtual), Czech Republic, 2nd June 2021.

Morrison, M. and Faulkner, A. (2021) “Inventing biomedical accuracy: between customisation and personalisation of advanced therapies” paper presented to the Association for Studies in Innovation, Science and Technology-UK (AsSIST-UK) conference 2021, held online 9th-10th August 2021.

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Bicudo, E.; Faulkner, A. and Li, P. “3D bioprinting.” MHRA Patient Forum. Medicines and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency, London, UK. 30 January 2020.

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Li, P (2020) ‘Intellectual property for humanity: a manifesto’, Annual Conference of the Sussex Centre for Information Governance Research (CIGR) (online Zoom presentation)

Li, P ‘3D bioprinting: intellectual property, regulation, and liability’ Bioprinting workshop of the BioMOD Project. Oxford, UK. 12 February 2020.

Morrison, M. “Continuity and disruption in the governance of (germline) gene editing”. “Experimenting on Future Children: Gene Editing in Human Reproduction” – Foundation Brocher, Hermance, Switzerland - 14-16 January 2020

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Morrison, M. (2020) “Legal and regulatory issues attending somatic medical uses of CRISPR” presented to the symposium ‘New genome editing technologies for medicine and agriculture – implication for society’ organised by the Lund University, Sweden, 13th October 2020.

Bicudo, E. “Bioprinting technology, regulation, and intellectual property.” International 3D Bioprinting Research Symposium. London, UK. 22 November 2019.

Bicudo, E. “Neuroimaging, software, and communication.” Book launch at Sussex Humanities Lab, University of Sao Paulo. Brighton, UK. 18 October 2019.

Faulkner, A; Bicudo, E and Li, P. “Emergence, ownership and governance: shaping the experimental space of 3D bioprinting’ BSA Annual Medical Sociology Conference, York, Sept 2019

Faulkner, A. 3DMedLive meeting ‘3D printing in surgery’ Oct 2019, London. Attended by businesses, NHS clinicians and various authorities including MHRA, NICE and NHS Executive. While not focused on bioprinting per se, was especially useful for accounts of the types of skills and arrangements that 3D printing is stimulating in the NHS

Li, P, ‘3D bioprinting patents and experimental space’ at Patents and emerging technologies workshop, Wellcome Collection, Nov 2019

Li, P. 3D bioprinting and biofabrication: from cellular models to tissue engineering applications, Bordeaux Nov 2019 Inserm workshop 258 entitled “3D bioprinting and biofabrication: from cellular models to tissue engineering applications” organized by Sylvain CATROS, Raphael DEVILLARD and Hugo OLIVEIRA

Li, P. Panel on ‘European health law and innovation: substantive aspects and embedding in national legal orders’ at EAHL 2019 Toulouse ‘Innovation and healthcare: new challenges for Europe’ 2019

Morrison, M. (2019) “CRISPR in Context: A critical historical perspective on the promise and utility of gene editing”, *We new utopians...gene editing and echoes of future life*, Goethe University, Germany. September 17-18, 2019.

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Other outputs and Impact

Bicudo, E. (2021). ‘Peek behind the paper – digital readiness in 3D bioprinting: software, governance and hospitals’ proto-clinical interfaces’ Interview given to RegMedNet

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Morrison, M. (2020) ‘Targeted policy support for emerging biomedical innovations’. Open Access Government. June 15. <https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/targeted-policy-support-for-emerging-biomedical-innovations/88436/>

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Morrison, M. (2019) ‘The promises and challenges of biomodifying technologies for the UK’. Open Access Government. September 13. <https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/biomodifying-technologies/68041/>

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Morrison, M. and Asquer, A. Guest editors on an open access special issue on “Regulation and Governance of Gene Editing Technologies (CRISPR, etc.)” for *Frontiers in Political Science* <https://www.frontiersin.org/research-topics/17742/regulation-and-governance-of-gene-editing-technologies-crispr-etc>

Michael Morrison was interviewed as an international expert for the Australian Research Council (ARC)-funded project “Genome editing: Formulating an Australian Community Response” in 2020 and also took part in the 2021 policy recommendations workshop for the same project

Collectively:

Contribution to UK Parliamentary Office of Science and Technology POST Note “Human germline genome editing” published January 2020 (see acknowledgement listed at <https://post.parliament.uk/research-briefings/post-pn-0611/>)

Contribution to POST Note “3D bioprinting in medicine” published March 2020 (see acknowledgements listed at <https://post.parliament.uk/research-briefings/post-pn-0620/>)